

Breeding wheat for organic farming: do we need other varieties with respect to end-use quality?

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Over the last three decades both the organic farmland as well as the organic market continuously increased to more than 15 million hectares and 45 billion Euros, respectively. Wheat is the most important crop in organic small grains production in Europe due to its essential role in human nutrition (1). The Farm to Fork Strategy of the European Green Deal aims to reach at least 25% of agricultural land under organic farming (2). Hitherto, only Austria has already reached >25% organic area, followed by Estonia and Sweden with >20%. By 2023, 17.5% of the total bread wheat acreage in Austria is organic with the significant major part cultivated with high quality wheat. In 2002, Austria launched as first country a new VCU test series exclusively under organic management for bread wheat as correlations between long-term conventional and organic trials revealed to be low especially for baking volume and nitrogen use efficiency (3). While under conventional management the correlation between protein content and rheological traits from the farino- and extensograph with baking volume is significant and high, it is not the case under organic management. Here, the highest correlation with baking volume was observed for the wet gluten content. Different regression slopes between protein content and baking volume for organically and conventional grown bread wheat, genotypic cross-over interactions between management systems with respect to end-use quality and changes in the classification of baking quality were observed also in Germany (4) and, thus, an organic VCU test was also established there 10 years ago. From these long-term observations it is evident that organic wheat production needs specific varieties to exploit most efficiently the genotype by management interaction not only with respect to grain yield but also with respect to end-use quality. The reasons for this interaction still await their exploration and revelation.

(1) David C, et al. (2012) *Sust Agric Rev* 11:43-62. doi: 10.1007/978-94-007-5449-2_3

(2) European Union (2020) *Farm to fork strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system.*

(3) Löschenberger F, et al. (2008) *Euphytica* 163:469-480. doi: 10.1007/s10681-008-9709-2

(4) Kempf H (2002) *Ber. 53. Tagung Vereinig. Pflanzenzüchter und Saatgutkaufleute Österreichs*, pp. 65-70.

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Marker-assisted introgression of the high protein content gene *Gpc-B1* and its effect on quality traits of organic wheat

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In organic wheat production, grain protein content (GPC) is generally lower than in conventional production due to lower nitrogen availability (1). We used the *Gpc-B1* gene from wild emmer (2) to evaluate its effect on ensuring high GPC and baking quality in organic wheat. The functional *Gpc-B1* allele was transferred from hard-red spring wheat 'Glupro' (USA) into winter wheats 'Spontan' (SPO; Germany) and 'Mv Kolompos' (KOL, Hungary). Allelic status of *Gpc-B1* was checked in 500 F_{3:4} plants of each cross by molecular markers (3,4) in order to develop bulks homozygous for the functional and non-functional alleles. Seeds of F_{3:6} bulks were distributed to project partners in fall 2022 for multi-environment trials. Here we report results of the F_{3:5} material from the Austrian seed multiplication trial 2022. GPC was increased by ≈1% by *Gpc-B1* (i.e. 15% vs 13.9% in SPO, 16.9% vs 15.9% in KOL). Mixing properties showed increased dough development times, peak energy, and reduced softening for *Gpc-B1* in both backgrounds, however, in SPO the effect was more pronounced. Results for dough extensibility showed contradictory results in the two genetic backgrounds, i.e. slightly increased dough resistance but reduced extensibility in SPO, whereas in KOL peak resistance was reduced and extensibility significantly increased. The preliminary results showed that *Gpc-B1* efficiently increased GPC and dough mixing properties in two different genetic backgrounds, however, effects were not coherent with respect to dough extensibility. The two recipient varieties used in this study are different especially with respect to their maturity but also baking quality which may be correlated with the different responses to the *Gpc-B1* introgression. Significant interactions of *Gpc-B1* with genotype and environment require an evaluation of this introgression in particular genotypes and environments which will happen in 2023.

(1) Mäder P, et al. (2007) *J Sci Food Agric* 87:1826-1835. doi: 10.1002/jsfa.2866

(2) Mesfin A, et al. (1999) *Crop Sci* 39:508-513. doi: 10.2135/cropsci1999.0011183X003900020035x

(3) Distelfeld A, et al. (2006) *New Phytol* 169:753-763. doi: 10.1111/j.1469-8137.2005.01627.x

(4) Rasheed A, et al. (2016) *Theor Appl Genet* 129:1843-1860. doi: 10.1007/s00122-016-2743-x

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XIV International Gluten Workshop

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Madrid, June 13th, 2023

Dear Colleagues and Friends,

We are delighted to announce that the 14th International Gluten Workshop will finally take place in Madrid in 2023.

Originally planned as a joint Iberian venture between Spain and Portugal, the event had to be postponed and rearranged due to the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic. The global impact and response to the pandemic, a human health crisis caused by a virus passed from animals, highlight the need for coordinated action across sectors to protect health and prevent disruption to food systems. It is paramount then that we keep global sustainability policies at the forefront of our minds when we discuss how to systemically promote health, as prescribed by the Quadripartite One Health Plan of Actions put forward by the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), the World Health Organization (WHO) and the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH).

Understanding the myriad aspects of wheat production, transformation, and utilization is of utmost importance in shaping diets worldwide. This workshop offers a valuable opportunity for researchers in this field to exchange experiences, establish connections, and explore collaborations to address the challenges facing global wheat crops. Since the global disruptions to travel and face-to-face meetings, it is even more crucial for us to come together and create a friendly and open academic environment. We are confident that this long-awaited meeting will provide an excellent platform for researchers studying all aspects of gluten and wheat quality.

We heartily thank the members of the Scientific Committee for their invaluable advice and assistance: Alison Lovegrove, Angela Juhasz, Bárbara Laddomada, Carlos Guzmán, Catherine Grand-Ravel, Eva Johansson, Heinrich Grausgruber, Marcelo Helguera, Maria Itria Ibba, Maryke Labuschagne, Tatsuya Ikeda, and Zhonghu He.

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The commitment to increase the internationalization of the 14th IGW has been accomplished with contributions from 29 countries. We continue to advocate for diversity and equality in research including through a Women in Wheat breakout session. The excellence of the conference will be underscored by a reflective session dedicated to the late Craig Morris. During this tribute, different speakers will summarize the great work Craig did in different areas over the years, the impact of his research, and the current research opportunities that have been enabled by his discoveries.

Lastly, we would like to express our appreciation to all the participants and authors whose research has contributed to creating such a high-quality scientific program. We are excited to welcome you to Madrid and wish you a successful workshop and a pleasant stay in this vibrant city.

The sharing of knowledge is guaranteed.

Sincerely,

Patricia Giraldo

Gilberto Igrejas

Chairs of the 14th International Gluten Workshop

